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Vegetable production systems in northern Côte d'Ivoire: Constraints, economic performance and integrated soil fertility management challenges

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ABSTRACT

Vegetable production plays a strategic role in food security and income generation in northern Côte d'Ivoire, although its performance remains strongly influenced by local social, agronomic, and environmental conditions. This study analyzes vegetable production systems in Sinématiali and Dikodougou using an integrated socio-economic and agronomic approach. A survey was conducted among 150 producers across six villages. Data collected included farmers' socio-demographic characteristics, cropping practices, production constraints, and economic performance of eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) and okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.). Results reveal a strong feminization of vegetable farming (70.66% in Sinématiali and 96% in Dikodougou), combined with low educational levels and a predominance of producers aged 41–70 years. Production systems are largely characterized by monocropping, ridge cultivation, and widespread use of chemical inputs. In Sinématiali, yields mainly range between 6.25 and 7.50 t/ha, with net profitability between 200,000 and 300,000 FCFA per 0.2 ha. In contrast, Dikodougou records lower yields (3.75–5.00 t/ha) and net returns not exceeding 200,000 FCFA per 0.2 ha. These findings indicate that economic performance is closely linked to cropping practices, access to inputs, and market conditions. They highlight the need for integrated soil fertility management strategies to enhance productivity while ensuring long-term sustainability of vegetable production systems.

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INTRODUCTION

Vegetable production constitutes a strategic pillar of agricultural systems in West Africa due to its contribution to food security, nutritional diversification, and income generation for households (FAO, 2020; Kubitzka *et al.*, 2024). In Côte d'Ivoire, particularly in the northern regions, vegetable farming has emerged as an adaptive strategy in response to climate variability affecting rainfed crops and as an economic alternative to traditional cash crop sectors (Dosso *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, vegetable production has a significant social dimension, especially for women, for whom it represents an important source of economic empowerment in contexts characterized by limited access to productive and land resources (De Bon *et al.*, 2010).

However, the rapid expansion of vegetable production systems has been accompanied by increasing intensification of agricultural practices, characterized by crop specialization, short production cycles, and cultivation on small land areas (Pretty *et al.*, 2018; Fuglie *et al.*, 2021). These strategies, widely observed in rural and peri-urban areas of Côte d'Ivoire, aim to meet growing market demand and secure short-term income (Kubitzka *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless, they raise important concerns regarding the agronomic and economic sustainability of farms, particularly in areas where access to inputs, technical support, and markets remains limited (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2014). Numerous studies have shown that poorly managed intensification in vegetable systems contributes to the progressive degradation of soil fertility, declining organic matter content, and increased dependence on chemical inputs, without necessarily leading to proportional improvements in yields or profitability (Bationo *et al.*, 2012; Pretty *et al.*, 2018). In West Africa, these dynamics are further reinforced by structural constraints such as climate variability, limited access to quality inputs, marketing difficulties, and logistical challenges related to the transport of agricultural products (Thornton *et al.*, 2014; Fuglie *et al.*, 2021). In Côte d'Ivoire, several studies have demonstrated that these constraints strongly affect the productive and economic

performance of vegetable systems, particularly in rural areas of the northern part of the country (Dosso *et al.*, 2024).

In this context, the analysis of vegetable production systems cannot be limited to the assessment of physical yields alone but must simultaneously integrate social, agronomic, and economic dimensions, as well as the constraints faced by producers. Such a systemic approach makes it possible to better understand disparities between productivity and profitability levels, as well as the trade-offs made by farmers according to their resources, agroecological environment, and market opportunities (Ostrom, 2009; FAO, 2020). Several authors emphasize that the profitability of vegetable production depends not only on production conditions but also on access to marketing channels and effective cost management, particularly at the scale of small cultivated areas (Kubitzka *et al.*, 2024). This study is framed within this analytical perspective and aims to characterize vegetable production systems in Sinématiali and Dikodougou (northern Côte d'Ivoire) in order to promote sustainable improvements in productivity and profitability while preserving natural resources. It analyzes the socio-demographic characteristics of producers, agronomic practices, climatic, technical, and organizational constraints, as well as the productive and economic performance of the main vegetable crops, particularly eggplant and okra, evaluated at a 0.2 ha scale.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was conducted in the Korhogo department, located in the Poro region in northern Côte d'Ivoire, near the borders with Mali and Burkina Faso. The climate is Sudanian–Guinean (Siené *et al.*, 2020), with mean annual rainfall ranging between 1,100 and 1,600 mm, and average annual temperatures varying from 24 to 33 °C. Natural vegetation is dominated by wooded savanna ecosystems developed on ferruginous tropical soils. These agroecological conditions provide favorable potential for vegetable production systems, particularly short-cycle crops.

The sub-prefectures of Sinématiali and Dikodougou were selected due to their importance in regional vegetable production and the diversity of cropping practices observed.

Data collection

Target population

The target population consisted of all vegetable producers operating in the study area.

Due to logistical constraints related to field surveys, the study focused on the accessible population of vegetable farmers active in the sub-prefectures of Sinématiali and Dikodougou.

Selection of survey sites

The study sites were purposively selected in collaboration with the National Agency for Rural Development Support (ANADER). Villages were chosen based on their importance in regional vegetable production and the diversity of cropping systems practiced.

Three villages (Nagbanavogo, Nagorigoh, and Pélébivogo) were selected in Sinématiali and three others (Bana, Diko, and Kadioha) in Dikodougou. This design allowed for meaningful inter-locality comparisons while maintaining relatively homogeneous agroecological conditions.

Selection of producers

Producers were selected in the sub-prefectures of Sinématiali and Dikodougou, where the Sénoufo population, which constitutes the majority ethnic group, plays a central role in agricultural activities, including vegetable production. This socio-cultural context influences labor organization, technical choices, and farming practices. The selection was based on official lists of vegetable producers provided by ANADER, ensuring the identification of active producers and improving sample representativeness.

Survey procedures

A semi-structured methodological approach combining quantitative and qualitative data was

adopted to comprehensively analyze the socio-economic and agronomic dimensions of vegetable production systems. This approach is particularly suitable in contexts characterized by high heterogeneity of farming practices. Data were collected between October and November 2022 through direct interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire covered socio-economic characteristics, cropping practices, input use, yields, production costs, and economic performance indicators.

Interviews were conducted in French or, when necessary, in local languages (Sénoufo and Malinké) to ensure accurate understanding of the questions. Direct field observations complemented the interviews to verify selected information.

A total of 150 vegetable producers were surveyed across six villages, with 25 producers interviewed per village.

Economic performance analysis

The economic profitability of eggplant and okra production was estimated on a 0.2 ha basis using the following equation:

$$NR = GP - TC$$

Where:

NR = Net return (FCFA)

GP = Gross product

TC = Total production cost

The gross product was calculated as:

$$GP = Y \times P$$

Where:

Y = Farmer-reported yield (t per 0.2 ha)

P = Average seasonal price observed during the rainy season (FCFA per ton)

Total cost breakdown

Total production cost was defined as:

$$TC = VC + FC$$

Where:

VC = Variable cost

FC = Fixed costs

Variable costs included seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, hired labor, family labor (valued at the prevailing local daily wage), and other operational expenses directly related to the production cycle. Fixed costs included depreciation of agricultural equipment and tools. Yields used in the analysis were based on farmers' self-reported estimates. These yields were not directly measured in the field, which may introduce potential reporting bias.

Statistical analysis

Collected data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 27.0. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed at a

significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ to assess differences between groups. When significant differences were detected, Tukey's post hoc test was applied for mean comparisons.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic characteristics of vegetable producers

The socio-demographic characteristics of vegetable producers in Sinématiali and Dikodougou are presented in Table 1. Vegetable production is predominantly carried out by women in both localities, accounting for $70.66 \pm 10.06\%$ of producers in Sinématiali and 96% in Dikodougou.

Table 1. Socio-demographic profile (%) of vegetable producers in Sinématiali and Dikodougou, Northern Côte d'Ivoire

Farmer classification	Gender	Age	Origin	Education level	Organization membership	Technical support
Sinématiali						
A	70.66±10.06 ^a	36.00±17.43 ^a	88.00±8.00 ^a	20.00±0.00 ^b	-	100.00±0.00
B	29.33±10.06 ^b	64.00±17.58 ^b	12.00±8.00 ^b	80.00±0.00 ^a	100.00±0.00	-
<i>p</i> -value	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS
Dikodougou						
A	96.00±4.00 ^a	42.66±16.10 ^b	95.33±3.05 ^a	25.34±12.22 ^b	66.66±57.73 ^b	25.33±22.27 ^b
B	4.00±4.00 ^b	57.34±16.10 ^a	4.66±3.00 ^b	74.66±12.22 ^a	33.34±57.73 ^a	76.00±22.27 ^a
<i>p</i> -value	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	0.04 S
Overall means						
A	83.33±7.02 ^a	39.33±15.01 ^b	88.50±0.86 ^a	22.66±6.11 ^b	33.33±28.86 ^b	62.00±11.13 ^a
B	16.66±7.02 ^b	60.66±15.01 ^a	11.66±0.76 ^b	77.33±6.11 ^a	66.66±28.86 ^a	38.00±11.13 ^b
<i>p</i> -value	<0.001 HS	0.15 NS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	0.05 S
Class identification						
A	Women	20–40	IP	Literate	NM	Yes
B	Men	41–70	NIP	Illiterate	CM	No

IP= Indigenous producers, NIP= Non-indigenous producers, NM= Non-member, CM= Cooperative member

Producers are largely indigenous to the area (88.50%) and mainly belong to the 41–70 age group (60.60%). The majority of farmers are illiterate (77.33%). Furthermore, 62% of producers reported receiving technical support, and 66.66% are members of a cooperative or producer group.

Agronomic characteristics of vegetable cropping systems

The agronomic characteristics of eggplant and okra production in Sinématiali and Dikodougou are presented in Table 2. In Sinématiali, analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed highly significant differences for certain agronomic practices ($p < 0.01$).

Monocropping is the dominant production system ($70.66 \pm 22.40\%$). Ridge cultivation is practiced by $92.00 \pm 10.58\%$ of producers, and $85.33 \pm 6.11\%$ rely on family labor. Vegetable production is carried out during both seasons of the year by $72.00 \pm 16.00\%$ of farmers, with two production cycles annually. Planting material includes improved varieties ($46.66 \pm 8.32\%$) or a combination of traditional and improved varieties ($52.00 \pm 10.52\%$), with no statistically significant difference between these proportions. Organo-mineral fertilization is practiced by $76.00 \pm 20.00\%$ of producers, while $24.00 \pm 20.00\%$ rely exclusively on mineral fertilizers. All producers ($100.00 \pm 0.00\%$) reported using chemical

pesticides. Cultivated areas are predominantly larger than 0.75 ha ($100.00 \pm 0.00\%$).

In Dikodougou, ANOVA also indicated highly significant differences for certain variables ($p < 0.01$), whereas others showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Monocropping is practiced by $68.00 \pm 28.84\%$ of producers. Ridge cultivation concerns $65.33 \pm$

50.01% of farmers, and $89.33 \pm 10.06\%$ rely on family labor. All producers carry out two production cycles per year ($100.00 \pm 0.00\%$) and predominantly use traditional varieties ($93.33 \pm 6.14\%$). Organo-mineral fertilization is adopted by $90.66 \pm 6.11\%$ of producers. The use of chemical pesticides is reported by $100.00 \pm 0.00\%$ of farmers. Cultivated areas are mainly between 0.25 and 0.75 ha ($60.00 \pm 4.00\%$).

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics (%) of vegetable production systems in Sinématiali and Dikodougou, Northern Côte d'Ivoire

Classes	Cropping system	Planting method	Labour	Planting period	Type of variety	Number of cycles	Type of fertilizer	Type of pesticide	Cultivated area
Sinématiali									
A	-	92.00 ± 10.58^a	85.33 ± 6.11^a	13.33 ± 10.06^b	1.33 ± 2.20^b	14.66 ± 8.32^b	-	-	-
B	29.33 ± 22.40^b	1.38 ± 2.30^b	2.00 ± 3.46^b	14.66 ± 15.14^b	16.66 ± 8.32^a	85.33 ± 8.32^a	24.00 ± 20.00^b	100.00 ± 0.00	-
C	70.66 ± 22.40^a	6.66 ± 8.32^a	12.66 ± 6.42^a	72.00 ± 16.00^a	52.00 ± 10.52^a	-	76.00 ± 20.00^a	-	100.00 ± 0.00
P-value	0.01 S	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS
Dikodougou									
A	11.33 ± 17.92^b	65.33 ± 50.01^a	89.33 ± 10.06^a	-	93.33 ± 6.14^a	-	-	-	36.00 ± 8.00^b
B	20.66 ± 29.14^b	1.38 ± 2.30^b	4.00 ± 4.00^b	-	1.33 ± 2.30^b	100.00 ± 0.00	12.66 ± 11.77^b	100.00 ± 0.00	60.00 ± 4.00^a
C	68.00 ± 28.84^a	33.33 ± 50.96^a	6.66 ± 6.11^b	100.00 ± 0.00	5.33 ± 4.61^b	-	90.66 ± 6.11^a	-	4.00 ± 6.92^c
P-value	<0.001 HS	0.24 NS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS
Overall means									
A	5.66 ± 14.57^b	78.66 ± 20.28^a	87.33 ± 4.16^a	6.66 ± 0.00^b	47.33 ± 2.30^a	7.33 ± 4.16^b	-	-	18.00 ± 4.00^c
B	24.99 ± 8.96^b	1.33 ± 1.15^b	3.00 ± 1.00^b	7.33 ± 0.00^b	24.00 ± 5.29^b	92.66 ± 4.16^a	18.33 ± 4.93^b	100.00 ± 0.00	30.00 ± 2.00^b
C	69.33 ± 14.42^a	20.00 ± 29.58^b	9.66 ± 4.99^b	86.00 ± 0.00^a	28.66 ± 4.16^b	-	83.38 ± 7.02^a	-	52.00 ± 3.46^a
P-value	<0.001 HS	0.01 S	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS
Class identification									
A	Rotation	Ridge planting	Family labour	Rainy season	Traditional	One	Organic	Biopesticide	≤ 0.25 ha
B	Intercropping	Bed planting	Hired labour	Dry season	Improved	Two	Mineral	Chemical	0.25-0.75 ha
C	Monocropping	Flat planting	Both	Both seasons	Both	Three	Organo-mineral	Both	≥ 0.75 ha

Values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Within each column, means followed by different letters (a, b, c) indicate significant differences based on Tukey's post hoc test at $\alpha = 0.05$. A, B and C refer to class categories. HS: highly significant ($p < 0.01$); S: Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS: Not Significant.

Economic performance of eggplant and okra

Productive and economic performance of eggplant and okra were assessed based on individual farmer-reported yields, converted into t/ha and analyzed using analysis of variance (Table 3).

Eggplant yield

The analysis of continuous eggplant yields revealed a significant difference between localities ($p < 0.05$). Producers in Sinématiali recorded average yields ranging between 6.25 and 7.50 t/ha, whereas those in Dikodougou obtained significantly lower yields, generally equal to or below 5 t/ha. Levene's test was used to assess homogeneity of variances. When this assumption was not met, Welch's robust correction was applied to ensure the validity of comparisons. From a descriptive perspective, the majority of producers in Sinématiali (58.66%) fell within the yield class of 1.25–1.50 t per 0.2 ha (6.25–7.50 t/ha), while in Dikodougou, 94.66% of producers were concentrated in the 0.75–1.00 t per 0.2 ha class (3.75–5.00 t/ha).

Okra yield

For okra, ANOVA also indicated a significant difference between localities ($p < 0.05$). Average yields in Sinématiali ranged between 6.25 and 7.50 t/ha, whereas in Dikodougou they were predominantly between 2.50 and 3.75 t/ha. The same diagnostic procedures used for eggplant (normality and variance homogeneity checks) were applied prior to ANOVA implementation. Descriptively, 66.66% of producers in Sinématiali belonged to the 1.25–1.50 t per 0.2 ha yield class, whereas 70.67% of producers in Dikodougou were concentrated in the 0.50–0.75 t per 0.2 ha class.

Economic profitability

Net return, calculated on the basis of individual continuous yields and total production costs (including both variable and fixed costs, as well as the valuation of family labor), reflected these productivity differences. In Sinématiali, most producers achieved a net return between 200,000

and 300,000 FCFA per 0.2 ha. In contrast, profitability levels in Dikodougou were predominantly equal to or below 200,000 FCFA per

0.2 ha. These economic differences are consistent with the yield gaps observed between the two localities.

Table 3. Productive and economic performance (%) of eggplant and okra cultivation in Sinématiali and Dikodougou, northern Côte d'Ivoire

Classes	Eggplant production level	Okra production level	Okra profitability level	Eggplant profitability level
Sinématiali				
A	8.00±8.00 ^{ab}	4.00±6.92 ^b	26.66±28.09 ^a	20.00±20.00 ^a
B	9.33±8.32 ^{ab}	8.00±6.92 ^b	48.06±46.07 ^a	58.66±37.16 ^a
C	20.00±20.00 ^{ab}	18.66±18.03 ^b	25.33±26.02 ^a	12.00±12.00 ^a
D	58.66±38.43 ^a	66.66±28.93 ^a	-	9.33±10.06 ^a
E	4.00±6.92 ^b	2.66±4.61 ^b	-	-
p-value	0.04 S	<0.001 HS	0.33 NS	0.08 NS
Dikodougou				
A	94.66±9.23 ^a	70.67±32.33 ^a	86.66±23.09 ^a	100.00±0.00
B	5.33±9.23 ^b	29.33±32.33 ^b	13.33±23.09 ^b	-
p-value	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	<0.001 HS	-
Class identification				
A	0.50-0.75 tonne	0.50-0.75 tonne	≤200,000	≤200,000
B	0.75-1.00 tonne	0.75-1.00 tonne	200,000-300,000	200,000-300,000
C	1.00-1.25 tonne	1.00-1.25 tonne	300,000-400,000	300,000-400,000
D	1.25-1.50 tonne	1.25-1.50 tonne	≥400,000	≥400,000
E	≥1.50 tonne	≥1.50 tonne	-	-

Profitability classes are expressed in FCFA. Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation. Means followed by different letters within the same column differ significantly according to Tukey's test at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$). HS: highly significant ($p < 0.01$); S: Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS: Not Significant.

Constraints affecting vegetable production

Constraints related to vegetable production in Sinématiali and Dikodougou are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Percentage distribution of vegetable producers according to reported production constraints in Sinématiali and Dikodougou, Northern Côte d'Ivoire

Climatic constraints were reported by 82% of producers in Sinématiali and 42% in Dikodougou. These mainly concern irregular rainfall patterns and

unfavorable temperature conditions. Marketing difficulties were mentioned by 92% of producers in Sinématiali and 80% in Dikodougou. Transport-related problems were reported by 96% of farmers in Sinématiali and 62% in Dikodougou. Limited access to agricultural inputs was identified as a constraint by 97% of producers in Sinématiali and 78% in Dikodougou. Declining soil fertility was reported by 75% of producers in Sinématiali and 76% in Dikodougou. Yields were perceived as low by 84% of producers in Sinématiali and 50% in Dikodougou. Land access constraints were reported by 24% of producers in Sinématiali and only 4% in Dikodougou.

DISCUSSION

The integrated analysis of social, agronomic, economic characteristics and production constraints in Sinématiali and Dikodougou reveals structural relationships between farmer profiles, cropping systems and the levels of yield and profitability observed. These relationships are embedded within a

constraining agroecological context typical of vegetable-producing areas in northern Côte d'Ivoire.

On the one hand, the strong involvement of women in vegetable production, particularly in Dikodougou, confirms the central role of this activity in rural household livelihood strategies.

The predominance of women in Ivorian vegetable systems can be attributed to the relatively low initial investment required, the possibility of cultivating small land areas, and the short production cycles that facilitate entry into the activity and ensure rapid capital turnover (De Bon *et al.*, 2010; FAO, 2020; Doss, 2018). The high proportion of indigenous producers further indicates strong territorial embeddedness and integration within local agricultural diversification dynamics.

Conversely, the relatively advanced age of producers and the high illiteracy rate constitute structural constraints that may limit the adoption of technical innovations and farm management optimization, as highlighted by Fuglie *et al.* (2021). Nevertheless, a substantial proportion of producers benefit from technical support (62%) and are organized within cooperatives or producer groups (66.66%). Collective organization and access to extension services appear to act as compensatory mechanisms, facilitating improved access to inputs and enhancing cropping practices in both localities.

From an agronomic perspective, production systems are predominantly characterized by monocropping, ridge cultivation, and two annual production cycles, reflecting a process of spatial and temporal intensification. While this strategy allows for the maintenance of acceptable production levels, it may increase pressure on soil fertility in the absence of integrated nutrient management (Pretty *et al.*, 2018; Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2014).

The widespread use of organo-mineral fertilizers can be interpreted as an adaptive response to progressive soil nutrient depletion. However, the effectiveness of

this strategy largely depends on the quality and stabilization level of organic amendments. The application of insufficiently stabilized organic inputs may alter soil microbial communities, disrupt biological balance, and indirectly influence the dynamics of soil-borne pathogens when management practices are not adequately controlled (Bonanomi *et al.*, 2010; Lazcano *et al.*, 2013; Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2014). In intensified vegetable systems, such biological imbalances may contribute to increased phytosanitary pressure.

Moreover, the systematic use of chemical pesticides observed in both localities reflects high pest and disease pressure. This trend, widely documented in vegetable systems across sub-Saharan Africa, indicates growing dependence on synthetic inputs to secure yields under conditions of high pest incidence and intensive production cycles (Damalas and Koutroubas, 2016; Jepson *et al.*, 2020; Fuhrmann *et al.*, 2021). Simplification of cropping systems may further increase vulnerability to pests and diseases.

This situation raises major environmental and health concerns, particularly regarding soil and water contamination and chronic exposure of producers to active substances. Such risks are extensively documented in intensified horticultural systems where frequent and sometimes poorly regulated pesticide use leads to measurable environmental impacts and health effects among farmers (Damalas and Koutroubas, 2016; Jepson *et al.*, 2020; Fuhrmann *et al.*, 2021).

Thus, the interaction between soil fertility management, biological soil balance, and reliance on phytosanitary inputs emerges as a central determinant of agronomic sustainability in the vegetable systems studied.

These social and agronomic factors are reflected in the economic performance observed, although interpretation requires contextualization. In Sinématiali, eggplant and okra yields (6.25–7.50 t/ha), along with corresponding profitability levels,

place this locality within an intermediate to relatively satisfactory performance range for semi-intensive rainfed systems.

These levels are consistent with yield ranges typically reported in smallholder rainfed horticultural systems across sub-Saharan Africa, where vegetable productivity often varies between 5 and 8 t/ha depending on access to inputs, extension services, and markets (Pretty *et al.*, 2018; Fuglie *et al.*, 2021).

In contrast, the lower yields recorded in Dikodougou (≤ 5 t/ha) correspond to the lower range of rainfed vegetable systems facing significant hydrological and organizational constraints. In several rural West African contexts characterized by limited water control and restricted access to quality inputs, yields between 3 and 5 t/ha are commonly reported (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2014; Fuglie *et al.*, 2021). The performance gap between the two localities therefore reflects differential access to productive resources rather than mere technical inefficiency.

Comparisons with other regions of the country should be made cautiously due to marked agro-climatic and structural differences. Peri-urban zones and irrigated schemes generally benefit from improved water control, better market integration, and more developed infrastructure, all of which are key determinants of horticultural performance. Under such conditions, okra yields exceeding 8 t/ha and net returns above 300,000 FCFA per 0.2 ha may be achieved when water management and market access are secured (Pretty *et al.*, 2018; Kubitza *et al.*, 2024).

Interregional disparities should therefore not be interpreted as simple evidence of lower technical efficiency among northern producers but rather as the expression of differentiated socio-ecological configurations. Agricultural system research demonstrates that productivity and profitability result from interactions among biophysical, institutional, and organizational factors (Ostrom, 2009; Fuglie *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, the relatively limited importance of land access constraints in both localities suggests that current limitations of vegetable production are more closely linked to technical productivity, water security, and market valorization than to land availability, in contrast to peri-urban contexts characterized by strong land pressure (Moustier and Danso, 2006).

In summary, vegetable production systems in Sinématiali and Dikodougou display genuine economic potential, as evidenced by the yield and profitability levels observed in Sinématiali. However, this potential remains partially constrained by structural and environmental factors. Sustainable performance improvement requires an integrated approach combining improved water security, sustainable soil fertility management, strengthened farmer organization, and enhanced market integration, in line with the principles of sustainable intensification (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2014; Pretty *et al.*, 2018). Interregional comparison should therefore be viewed not as a normative ranking exercise but as an analytical tool for identifying structural determinants of productivity and context-specific levers for improvement.

CONCLUSION

This study provided an integrated characterization of vegetable production systems in Sinématiali and Dikodougou in northern Côte d'Ivoire through the analysis of social, agronomic, and economic dimensions. The results highlight the strong involvement of women, the marked local embeddedness of producers, and a relatively high level of collective organization despite limited educational capital.

Agronomically, production systems are predominantly based on monocropping, ridge cultivation, and two annual cycles under predominantly rainfed conditions. Productive performance observed in Sinématiali (6.25-7.50 t/ha) reflects a relatively satisfactory level within semi-intensive systems, whereas lower yields recorded in

Dikodougou (≤ 5 t/ha) illustrate the combined effects of climatic and organizational constraints reported by producers.

These disparities may be related to differences in water availability and market access conditions rather than to intrinsic differences in farmers' technical capacity.

Overall, the findings suggest that improving vegetable production systems in northern Côte d'Ivoire would benefit from a more integrated approach that considers agronomic, economic, and organizational dimensions to enhance long-term sustainability and resilience.

RECOMMENDATION(S)

The findings suggest that improving water management should be a priority in order to reduce rainfall dependence and stabilize yields, particularly in Dikodougou. The development of small-scale irrigation systems could significantly enhance productivity.

Strengthening integrated soil fertility management practices, combining organic and mineral inputs, is also essential to maintain soil productivity and reduce long-term degradation.

Capacity building and technical training programs, especially targeting women producers, should be reinforced to improve production efficiency and farm management.

In addition, promoting safer and more rational pesticide use is necessary. Training on integrated pest management (IPM) and stricter supervision of pesticide handling would help reduce environmental and health risks associated with chemical inputs.

Finally, improving farmers' access to markets and quality inputs through stronger producer organizations would enhance the economic viability of vegetable production systems in northern Côte d'Ivoire.

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